

DIFFERENCES OF TRANSLATION PHRAEOLOGICAL UNITS (IDIOMS) FROM ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: An idiom is a phrase that, when taken as a whole, has a meaning you wouldn't be able to deduce from the meanings of the individual words. That is why we face difficulties while translating idiom from SL to TL. Because, idioms are connected with cultural beliefs and traditions. To translate accurately, you have to know its origin meaning before translation. In this article we will discuss concerning the main differences of Uzbek and English ideoma while translating with the right way.

Key words: phraseologism, idioms, complete, partial, absence, cultural difference.

INTRODUCTION

IDIOMS are very essential part of the language. Due to the fact that they can help to make interesting of our context or daily conversation. Without IDIOMS the sentences would be always at the same tone and they are able to boost the emotional colouring of main meaning. The master of English Rachel Mitchell think that IDIOMS, in fact, the word phrases that don't mean exactly what they sound what they mean. To give the examples we can say that "one foot in the grave" or "when pigs fly" and such kind of word phrases are real IDIOMS. The use of idioms is a high-level skill. Using them properly not overusing. However, when it comes to translate them from one language to another one, it seems so challenging because of their ambiguous meaning. To translate accurately, you have to know its origin meaning before translation. For example, "When pigs fly" is translated into Uzbek as a "Tuyani dumi yerga tekkanda". Why is it totally different? Answer to this question is CULTURAL DIFFERENCE. Both of them give exact meaning in these languages, but in different forms. In western countries pigs are common, so they easily understand the meaning. As you know pigs are heavyweight animal, it is impossible them to fly and it implies to things never happen. But if we use this exact idiom in eastern countries, they may not understand. So what should we do?

There are 4 strategies to translate idioms:

1. Using an idiom of similar meaning and form. In this strategy, translator tries to find an idiom equivalent in TL in nearly same form. For example, "drag your feet" means to do something slowly, because you don't want to do it. In Uzbek language, there is "oyog'ini tirab olmoq" will be an alternative idiom and it is in similar form. There is no opaque word to make us confused.

2. Using an idiom similar meaning but in different form. That means an idioms gives the same meaning but with different words and forms. For example, "Skate on thin ice" means to take a big risk. In Uzbek language it has nearly same equivalent "Qil ustida yurmoq". "Thin ice" and "Qil" (a strand of hair) give same meaning but in different ways.

3. Paraphrasing. Not always we can not find equivalents like above. In that case we use paraphrasing strategy to keep an idiom meaning in TL language too. For example, " At the eleventh hour" means at the latest possible moment, is paraphrased to Uzbek as a "So'ngi daqiqalarda". We just transformed idiom's meaning word by word into Uzbek. Additionally, everyone can boost their vocabulary by using paraphrasing, using ideoms and can improve pronunciation too.

4. Omission. This is the last option, if you couldn't find equivalent or there is no way to paraphrasing. For example, " Can not make head and tails" in Uzbek will be omitted "head and tails" and we will just give meaning like "Anglay olmaslik". If we paraphrase, it may cause misunderstanding.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Phraseologisms are the language units that take the first place in the scale of "difficult to translate language units". Translation scientists recommend to study the phraseological units in SL by dividing them into three groups and turn to TL:

1. Complete compatibility - the meaning is completely the same
2. Partial compliance. - partial the same
3. Absence conformity (or inconsistency). - there's no any equivalence of meaning two different languages.

The provision of phraseologisms in translation is mainly characteristic of the first type of equivalence, that is, the main goal in this translation is the complete preservation of the purpose of communication in the translation. When translating phraseological units, the following methods are used:

- Literal translation;
- Analogous translation;
- Annotated translation;

1. Complete compatibility is the presence of stable equivalents of phraseological units in one language in the second language.

For example:

1. Crows don't pick crow's eyes - qarg'a qarg'ani ko'zini cho'qimaydi.
2. There is no rose without thorn- atirgulning ham tikoni bor.

In this examples we can say that their meaning is completely the same as their written version. In addition, their translating is also possible with their correct meaning in both languages. Other type of translation methods would help to identify the way of translation. Owing to the fact that without them it's more difficult to translate correctly.

2. The degree to which phraseological units in the same language are compatible. The lack of a complete translation into another language for phraseological units (PU) or the existence of a partially translated version in TL.

A phraseological unit in English may occasionally be fully compatible in another language while being **partially compatible** in Uzbek.

For example: From head to toe is translated as "с ног до головы". If this phrase is found in the translation from Russian to Uzbek, it will be translated from scratch into Uzbek. So, it can be seen that the Burmese phraseology, which is partially compatible with Russian in English, can be completely translated into Uzbek in English. Example: To fish in troubled waters /ideoma / loyqa suvda baliq tutmoq.

Absence is the complete absence of TL equivalents of PU in SL and the meeting of realias belonging to SL (non-equivalent lexical combinations) in the structure of these units. Such an PU is calculated from methods of giving an equivalent lexicon. For instance, in to shakes of lambs tail- bir zumda.

Now, we can analyse the different and the same translation of meaning English and Uzbek idioms, obviously.

1. To kill two birds with one stone- Bir o'q bilan ikki quyonni urmoq
2. Sitting duck- Oson o'lja
3. To chicken out- Qo'rqqanidan yoki xavotirlanganidan orqaga qaytmoq
4. Fly on the wall- Payqab bo'lmaydigan
5. Bee's knees- Eng zo'ri
6. To make a beeline- Maqsad sari olg'a bormoq
7. A wild goose chase- Somondan igna qidirgandek befoyda izlamoq
8. To take bull by the horns- Mashaqqatlarga mardonavor turmoq
9. To horse around- Shataloq otmoq
10. Until the cows come home- Uzoq vaqtdan beri

11. Dark horse- Ataladan suyak chiqdi
12. Hold your horses- Shoshilma
13. Straight from the horses mouth- Anniq guvohi bo'lgan insondan eshitmoq
14. In to shakes of lambs tail- Bir zumda
15. To go to the whole hog- Oxirigacha bormoq

Fixed compound translation is free compound translation is different from doing. From talking about the translation of stable compounds. First of all, to distinguish between its own and figurative or figurative types must fixed in its meaning based on the principles discussed above. The most important one of the principles is not to forget the norms of the translation language. The translation of mobile or figurative fixed compounds is separate requires attention. The main feature of such expressions is their with the difficulty of understanding the meaning from the sum of its components is characterized. The meaning of stable compounds is taken separately it comes not from the words, but from the sum of my words. To the image the text is expressed and stylistically based on fixed combinations ensures that it is colorful. Color of the original text It is also reflected in the translation and the full range of means of expression requires storage. The translator makes the text expressive and colorful in order to ensure that there is an adequate image in the translated text it is necessary to find a variant of the compounds. In the literature published on the theory of translation that there are four ways to form such compounds information is provided (L. Barkhudarov, V. Komissarov, Fiterman, Levitskaya, O. Petrova and others). They are as follows:

- 1) keep the image as it is;
- 2) the image is partial change;
- 3) replacing the image with a completely different image
- 4) not keeping the image completely in the translation or omitting it.

1. Generally, universal or international images are filled in the translation. Such phraseological units are historical, legendary, religious, will be based on mystical, mythological and the like. For example, "in the seventh heaven" - "yettinchi osmonda". Such phraseology units are called the translated language equivalents of the original. There are almost no phraseological units with complete equivalents in translation does not cause any problems, because they are stylistic and pragmatic from aspects to the same value, meaning, method of expression and influence will have. Sometimes the phraseological unit of the original image is translated into the language there will be an opportunity to save even if there is no alternative. To this can be achieved by calque. For example, "nothing comes out of the sack but what

was in it" - "qozonda bori cho'michga chiqadi". This method is figurative if the meaning of the phraseological unit is transparent, that is, it can be used only if it is easily understood by everyone. Phraseological although the words in the units are used figuratively, if their dictionary meaning is clear, when translating it. The use of copying is the text, the information in the text and makes it easier to understand the idea in the text, alternative translation provides.

2. In most cases, the original and translation languages have the same idea are expressed, but they differ from each other in their images. Both of them have the same figurative meaning. Such as, the slight difference between the images is not taken into account, in this case, the image in the phraseological unit being translated to be more precise, it undergoes a partial change in the translation.

3. Language wealth of each nation, including phraseological units its history, culture, traditions, lifestyle, mentality and reflects characteristic features and so on. For everyone the same thoughts are expressed differently by different peoples: Uzbeks "tuyani dumi yerga tekkanda", qizil qor yoqqanda", but in english language these phraseological words use as a " when pigs fly". Lexical units in both phraseological expressions are similar to each other, especially, although "camel and red snow" are not completely correct, "action, event that never happens" is the main is an opinion. Most of the words in phraseological units are used as a secondary element.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, even though, idiomatic units are one of the hard parts of translational works, they can help to collapse our ideas in one sentence. If we use the special ways of translation phraseological units, it gets more easier than we think. In addition, PU mostly have to take an important place in literal translation and daily conversation.

References:

1. Sh.Sirojiddinov, G. Odilova // Badiiy tarjima asoslari.-Toshkent, 2011. 101-110 p.
2. S.Vlaxov, S. Florin// Neperevodimoye v perevode.- Moskva,1980. 179 p.
3. www.grammarly.com